

Synthesis and Spectroscopic Investigations on Bis-dithiocarbamato Complexes of Di-*p*-*tert*-butylphenyltin(IV)

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Bis-*p*-*tert*-butylphenyltin(IV)-bis-dithiocarbamato complexes of the $R_2Sn(IV)[S_2CNR'R'']_2$, where R = *p*-*t*-Bu Ph.; R' = R'' = Me, Et, isopropyl, piperidine, morpholine, 2,6-dimethylmorpholine, 4-methylpiperidine or *N*-methylpiperazine; R' = Me, Et or *i*-Pr and R'' = CH₃, C₆H₅; R' = Me, Et and R'' = C₆H₅; have been prepared and their ir, ¹Hnmr and Mossbauer spectral studies were made. The results indicate an anisobidentate(unsymmetrical) mode of bonding for the dithiocarbamate moiety in these complexes.

A great deal of work has been reported on the synthesis and structural investigation of organotin(IV) dithiocarbamates since the first report on the synthesis of phenyltin dithiocarbamates by Kupchik and Calabretta¹. Unlike metal dithiocarbamates, a study of organotin(IV) carbamates and Sn(IV)-*N,N*-disubstituted-dithiocarbamate¹⁻¹⁰ reveals that the dithiocarbamate group acts as either monodentate, bidentate (or chelating) or anisobidentate ligand. Various spectroscopic techniques such as ir^{2,7,8}, ¹H nmr^{5,8}, Mössbauer⁷⁻¹⁴ and X-ray diffraction¹⁵⁻¹⁸ have been employed to find out the mode of bonding of the dithiocarbamate (dtc) moiety.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and spectroscopic investigations of some new diorganotin(IV) dithiocarbamates of the type $R_2Sn(IV)[S_2CNR'R'']_2$, where (i) R' = R'' = Me, Et, *i*-Pr, C₆H₅, isopropyl, piperidine, morpholine, 2,6-dimethylmorpholine, 4-methylpiperidine or *N*-methylpiperazine; (ii) R' = Me, Et or *i*-Pr, and R'' = CH₃, C₆H₅; and (iii) R' = Me, Et, and R'' = C₆H₅. 'Anisobidentate' mode of bonding of dtc has been established by various spectral measurements.

Experimental

Synthesis of complexes :

Sodium salts of the *N,N*-dialkyl- or alkylaryl-dithiocarbamates were prepared¹⁹ by the reaction of equimolar amounts of the respective secondary amine, carbon disulphide and sodium hydroxide in aqueous medium at 10–15°.

Tetra-p-tert-butylphenyltin(IV): Sodium (18.4 g, 0.8 mol) in the form of sand in benzene was taken

in a three-necked flask fitted with a stirrer, a reflux condenser and dropping funnel, and a mixture of tin tetrachloride (anhydrous) (26.05 g, 0.1 mol) and *p*-*tert*-butylbromobenzene (85.2 g, 0.4 mol) was added dropwise with continuous stirring over a period of 30 min. It was gently warmed initially and then refluxed for 3 h, cooled and filtered. Solvent was removed by distillation. A white crystalline solid compound obtained was recrystallised from benzene, (85%), m.p. 260°.

Bis-p-tert-butylphenyltin(IV) dichloride: It was prepared by the disproportionation reaction. Tetra-*p*-*tert*-butylphenyltin(IV) (65 g, 0.1 mol) and anhydrous tin tetrachloride (26.85 g, 0.1 mol) were taken in a sealed tube and was heated for 4 h at 240° and then cooled. The resulting compound was recrystallised from ether, (80%) m.p. 150°.

Di-p-tert-butylphenyl-N,N-dithiocarbamate: All the complexes were prepared by the method outlined below for di-*p*-*tert*-butylphenyltin(IV)-bis-*N,N*-dimethyldithiocarbamate. To a solution of di-*p*-*tert*-butylphenyltin(IV) dichloride (4.55 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added sodium salt of *N,N*-dimethyldithiocarbamate (2.86 g, 0.02 mol) in acetone (60 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 1 h and then filtered. The solvent was removed under vacuum to leave a solid. The complex was purified by dissolving in tetrahydrofuran and subsequent reprecipitation from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°), yielded white crystalline solid, (90%), m.p. 210°. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined microanalytically, and tin and sulphur were estimated gravimetrically as SnO₂ and barium sulphate, respectively (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Compd *	M.p. °C	Analys s % . Found/(Calcd.)				
			C	H	N	S	Sn
1.	L Sn [S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₃] ₂	210	50.01 (49.94)	6.02 (6.08)	4.56 (4.48)	20.22 (20.49)	19.02 (19.00)
2.	L ₂ Sn [S ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₅) ₃] ₂	178	53.02 (52.88)	6.82 (6.75)	4.20 (4.11)	19.03 (18.80)	17.50 (17.43)
3.	L Sn [S ₂ CN(C ₃ H ₇) ₃] ₂	98	56.03 (55.38)	7.41 (7.32)	3.88 (3.80)	17.68 (17.37)	16.32 (16.11)
4.	L Sn [S ₂ CN(CH ₃) (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₂] ₂	181	58.98 (58.71)	6.02 (5.92)	3.57 (3.60)	16.71 (16.48)	15.49 (15.28)
5.	L Sn [S CN(C ₂ H ₅) (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₂] ₂	165	58.96 (59.65)	6.29 (6.21)	3.55 (3.47)	14.97 (15.91)	14.48 (14.75)
6.	L Sn [S ₂ CN(C ₃ H ₇) (C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₂] ₂	104	59.82 (60.51)	6.60 (6.49)	3.29 (3.36)	14.95 (15.37)	14.07 (14.26)
7.	L Sn [S ₂ CN(CH ₃) (C ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₂	185	58.05 (57.70)	5.75 (5.61)	3.82 (3.74)	16.99 (17.10)	16.12 (15.85)
8.	L Sn [S ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₅) (C ₆ H ₅) ₂] ₂	198	59.12 (58.71)	6.03 (5.92)	3.70 (3.61)	15.07 (16.48)	15.45 (15.28)
9.	L Sn [S ₂ CNC ₄ H ₉ O] ₂	110	51.12 (50.80)	5.97 (5.90)	4.01 (3.95)	17.85 (18.06)	16.33 (16.75)
10.	L Sn [S ₂ CNC ₄ H ₉ (CH ₃) ₂] ₂	220	54.11 (53.35)	6.39 (6.54)	3.62 (3.66)	16.52 (16.74)	15.75 (15.52)
11.	L Sn [S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₄ CH ₃] ₂	99	51.93 (52.27)	6.61 (6.53)	7.69 (7.62)	17.66 (17.42)	15.89 (16.16)
12.	L Sn [S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₃] ₂	121	55.01 (54.49)	6.39 (6.50)	4.01 (3.97)	18.37 (18.16)	17.08 (16.84)
13.	L ₂ Sn [S ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₄ CH CH ₃] ₂	161	56.21 (55.68)	6.67 (6.82)	3.89 (3.82)	17.27 (17.47)	16.37 (16.20)

*L = *p*-[(CH₃)₃ C C₆H₄]₂; all compds are white crystalline solids

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	I S mm s ⁻¹	Q S. mm s ⁻¹	Resonance signals due to tert butyl-phenyl protons (τ ppm)			Proton signals* due to NR'R'' protons (τ ppm)			
			Sn-C ₆ H ₄		-(CH ₃) ₃ C	-CH ₃	-CH ₂	-CH	-C ₆ H ₄
			H _o (d)	H _m (d)	(s)				(s)
1	1.43	2.83	2.20	2.64	8.68	6.50	-	-	-
2	1.49	2.75	2.10	2.62	8.77	8.6t	6.12q	-	-
3	1.52	2.61	2.25	2.65	8.75	8.60d	-	5.30m	-
4	1.40	2.71	2.15	2.50	8.71	6.70s	5.02s	-	2.75
5	1.46	2.85	2.20	2.62	8.85	8.65t	6.20q 5.05s	-	2.70
6	1.55	2.68	2.25	2.65	8.85	8.65d	5.1s	6.22m	2.9
7	1.42	2.89	2.15	2.58	8.6	6.6s	-	-	2.7
8	1.45	2.96	2.25	2.60	8.8	8.60t	6.20q	-	2.75
9	1.50	2.66	2.18	2.70	8.70	-	6.05(N-CH ₃) 5.40(O-CH ₃)	-	-
10	1.29	2.76	2.15	2.65	8.71	8.85d	5.25 7.20	6.35m	-
11	1.53	2.82	2.10	2.60	8.6	7.8	6.0t(N-CH ₃) 7.4t	-	-
12	1.35	2.78	2.05	2.58	8.7	-	6.15(N-CH ₃) 8.36(C-CH ₃)	-	-
13	1.28	2.86	2.18	2.68	8.80	9.01	5.3d(N-CH ₃) 6.92t(C-CH ₃)	8.5m	-

* s = singlet, d = doublet, m = multiplet, q = quartet, t = triplet

Physicochemical measurements: Infrared spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer grating spectrometer using pressed discs for solid compounds in the region 4000–250 cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer at a sweep width of 900 Hz using TMS as internal standard, while the Mossbauer spectra were recorded as reported earlier⁶. Spectra

were recorded in triplicate and the values given in Table 2 are the average values.

Results and Discussion

Diorganotin dithiocarbamates of the type R₂Sn(IV)[S₂CNR'R'']₂ have been prepared in good yield by the reaction of diorganotin dichloride

and anhydrous sodium salt of the respective dithiocarbamic acid in acetone,

All these complexes are white crystalline solids with sharp melting points (Table 1). They are highly soluble in common organic solvents and are quite stable in dry and inert atmosphere at room temperature.

Ir spectra: Infrared spectroscopy along with other spectroscopic techniques (*e.g.* Mössbauer, 1H nmr *etc.*) is a powerful technique to distinguish between the different resonating structures of dithiocarbamate moiety in various metallic or organometallic dithiocarbamate complexes. In the ir spectra of the complexes, three main regions are important: (i) $1550-1450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is associated with the thioureide band due to ν_{C-N} vibration of $S_2C=NR'R''$ ligand, (ii) $1050-950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ associated with ν_{C-S} vibration, and (iii) $400-350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ associated with ν_{M-S} vibration. The ν_{C-N} band at 1500 cm^{-1} assigned to thioureide moiety²⁰ is now considered as vibration or a polar structure^{21,22}. The position of this band mainly depends on the arrangement of sulphur atoms (i) around the central metal atom (the order being planar > tetrahedral > octahedral > distorted octahedral or pyramidal), (ii) size of the R group on nitrogen²³, and (iii) the electronic properties of the NR_2 group²⁴. A splitting in this region indicates the presence of a unidentate dithiocarbamate ligand or the presence of both monodentate and bidentate ligand²⁴. However, the presence of a strong band in this region is an indication of the bidentate or anisobidentate character of the ligand⁶. Only one band appearing in the region $1050-950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was considered characteristic of symmetrically bonded bidentate ligand¹⁰. However, two bands indicate one uncomplexed C=S and the other complexed C-S group. Therefore, appearance of two bands $\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a separation of more than 20 cm^{-1} indicates the monodentate mode of bonding. Later on, this criteria was modified to accommodate the cases having unsymmetrical bonding of the ligand, *e.g.* $Ti(Et_2dtc)_4$ or of ligands of different denticity in the same complex, *e.g.* $Sn(R_2dtc)_4$ ²⁵⁻²⁷. It was suggested that the dtc ligand would be monodentate only if the separation value of the two bands, present in 1000 cm^{-1} region, is more than 20 cm^{-1} and a separation value less than 20 cm^{-1} is an indication either of an unsymmetric ligand or ligand with mixed denticity²⁵⁻²⁷.

For the present complexes only one band due to $\nu_{C-N} \sim 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and one broad band or two bands with a separation value of 5 cm^{-1} due to ν_{C-S} at $\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were observed. This broadening of 1000 cm^{-1} band may be explained as although both the sulphur atoms of the dtc group participate in bonding to the tin metal atom but there is a

slight difference in the Sn-S bond lengths, resulting in a corresponding difference in C-S bond lengths for both the sulphur atoms. The difference may however be too small to resolve the band into two peaks. The two M-S stretching bands were observed in the region $400-350\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The two bands at $\sim 580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 560 cm^{-1} were assigned to $\nu_{asy}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ and $\nu_{sym}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$.

1H nmr spectra: 1H nmr spectra of the complexes (Table 2) exhibit two types of signals, *i.e.* due to Sn-tert-butylphenyl group and NR_2 protons. Tert-butylphenyl group in all these complexes is characterised by the presence of three types of proton signal, *i.e.* a singlet at τ 8.70 (due to protons of the *para* substituted-tert-butyl group), a doublet at τ 2.1-2.5 (due to *ortho*-substitution) and a doublet at τ 2.5-2.68 (due to the *meta*-protons of the phenyl ring). The N-bonded R groups are equivalent in all these complexes because of the following observations. There appears only a singlet at τ 6.50-6.70 due to the N-CH₃ protons of 1, 4 and 7 complexes, while in the analogous ethyl-dtc complexes, namely 2 and 5, only one type of quartet at $\tau \sim 6.25$ (due to N-CH₃ protons). There also appears triplet at $\tau \sim 8.65$ (due to CH₃ protons of the ethyl group). In case of methylbenzyl, ethylbenzyl, *i*-propylbenzyl, methylphenyl and ethylphenyl complexes⁴⁻⁸, the presence of a singlet at $\tau \sim 2.70-2.90$ is correlated with phenyl protons, whereas the proton signals due to CH₂ fragment of the benzyl group (compounds 4-6) appear at τ 5.01-5.1. The *N*-isopropyl group in complexes 3 and 6 is well characterised by a heptet at $\tau \sim 5.30-6.22$ due to N-C-H protons and a doublet at $\tau \sim 8.60$ due to methyl protons. The presence of two types of proton signal in morpholine complex at $\tau \sim 6.05$ (N-CH₃ protons) and 6.40 (O-CH₂ protons) (due to NR₂ protons) again confirms the equivalence of the morphenyl group. 2,6-Dimethyl morpholine group in the complex (10) is identified with the presence of two types of resonance signals at τ 5.25 and 7.20 due to N-CH₂ protons, a complex multiplet at $\tau \sim 6.35$ due to CH protons and a doublet at $\tau \sim 8.75$ due to CH₃ protons. The piperidine group in compound 12 is identified with the appearance of two sharp signals at $\tau \sim 6.15$ (N-CH₂ protons) and 8.36 (C-CH₂ protons). A doublet at $\tau \sim 5.3$ (N-CH₂ protons), a triplet at ~ 6.92 (C-CH₂ protons), a multiplet at ~ 8.5 (CH protons) and a doublet at ~ 9.0 (C-CH₂ protons) characterise the presence of 4-methylpiperidine group in compound 13. The *N*-methylpiperazine group in compound 11 is inferred from the presence of two types of proton signals, *i.e.* one triplet at $\tau \sim 6.0$ due to the CH₃ protons bonded to the N of the dtc group and another triplet at $\tau \sim 7.4$ due to CH₂ protons on another nitrogen atom of the piperazyl group. The CH₃ protons show a singlet at $\tau \sim 7.8$. The equivalence of the R' group of the dtc moiety illustrates that these complexes are

stereochemically non-rigid at least at ambient temperature.

Mössbauer spectra: Mössbauer data including isomer shift, quadrupole splitting of diorganotin bisdithiocarbamates are given in Table 2. All the spectra consist of well resolved doublets indicating the lack of cubic symmetry of the charge distribution around the metal atom in all these complexes. The isomer-shift values are well within the range of characteristic of Sn^{IV} species. From the extensive data available²⁸⁻³⁰, the tin complexes of the type R_2SnX_4 can exist in *cis*- and *trans*-structures and quadrupole splitting has been found to be very useful in assigning the configuration of various organotin(IV) complexes. In the hexacoordinated complexes of the type R_2SnX_4 , it has been established on the basis of theoretical calculations as well as experimental results²⁸⁻³⁰ that for octahedral complexes with *trans*-R groups, the observed quadrupole splitting lies in the range $3.5 < \frac{1}{2} e^2qQ < 4.6 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$, on the other hand for the corresponding *cis*-compounds the quadrupole splitting lies in the range $1.5 < \frac{1}{2} e^2qQ < 2.2 \text{ mm s}^{-1}$. This is in agreement with the point-charge model which show that $Q_S(\text{trans}) = 2 Q_S(\text{cis})$.

The observed quadrupole splitting for di-*p* tert-butylphenyltin(IV) dithiocarbamate complexes are smaller than those observed for axially symmetric *trans*-octahedral complexes of the type R_2SnX_4 and larger than those observed for the analogous *cis*-configuration. The other geometry which suggests itself is that of distorted tetrahedral configuration in which the two dtc ligand acts as unidentate moieties with a single tin-sulphur σ -bond having the second sulphur atom in each ligand in a non-bonding orientation. Such a structure can however be ruled out on the basis of data³¹ on dialkyl tin(IV) bis-thiols. The observed quadrupole splittings for $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}(\text{SCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$, $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{Sn}(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ are 1.65, 1.59 mm s^{-1} , respectively, at 80 K and it is concluded that this magnitude of QS. parameter is properly associated with a distorted tetrahedral structure for dialkyltin compounds having two tin-sulphur σ -bonds. The present data can be understood in terms of two different tin-sulphur bond while the other is with a considerable weaker bonding interaction between the metal and the ligand described by De Vries and Herber¹¹ as anisobidentate (this is also evident from ir data of these complexes). Under these conditions it is probable that the C-Sn-C bond angle will depart significantly from 180° and C_{2v} symmetry no longer obtains in these compounds.

On the basis of the information obtained from ir, ^1H nmr and Mössbauer studies, it can be suggested that in these di-*p*-tert-butylphenyltin-bisdithiocarbamate complexes, both the sulphur atoms of the dtc group participate in the bonding

with different Sn-S interactions (unsymmetric or anisobidentate bonding character),

References

1. E. J. KUPCHIK and P. J. CALABRETTA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 6, 973.
2. G. MANCOTRIGIANO, G. C. PELTACANI, C. PRETI and G. TOSI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, 48, 1018.
3. D. PERRY and R. A. GAENANGEL, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 13, 185, and reference therein.
4. I. OJIMA, I. ONISHI, T. IWAMOTO, N. INAMOTO and K. TAMANI, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1970, 6, 63.
5. F. BONATI, R. UGO and S. CENINI, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1967, 9, 395.
6. G. DOMAZETTIS, R. J. MAGES and B. D. JAMES, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1977, 141, 57.
7. C. P. SHARMA, N. KUMAR, S. WADHWA and B. S. GARG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 247.
8. C. P. SHARMA, N. KUMAR, M. C. KANDPAL, S. CHANDRA and V. G. BHIDE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 923.
9. F. BONATI, G. MINGHETTE and S. CENINI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 2, 375.
10. F. BONATI and R. UGO, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1967, 10, 257.
11. J. L. K. F. DE VRIES and R. H. HERBER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 2458.
12. C. P. SHARMA, N. KUMAR, M. C. KANDPAL, S. CHANDRA and V. G. BHIDE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 1092.
13. M. HONDA, K. KOMURA, V. KAWASKI, T. TANAKA and R. OKAWARA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 3231.
14. T. KIMURA, N. YASUOKA, N. KASAI and M. KAKUDE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1972, 45, 1649.
15. E. O. SCHLEMPER, Private communication.
16. J. POTENZA, R. J. JOHNSON and D. MASTROPALO, *Acta Crystallogr., Part B*, 1976, 32, 941.
17. C. S. HARRELD and E. O. SCHLEMPER, *Acta Crystallogr., Part B*, 1971, 27, 1964.
18. P. F. LINDLEY and P. CARR, *J. Cryst. Mol. Struct.*, 1974, 4, 173.
19. H. L. KLOPPING and G. J. M. VANDERKERK, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1951, 70, 917.
20. H. M. RANDLE, R. G. FOUTER, N. FUSON and J. R. DANGEL, "Infrared Determination of Organic Structure", Van Nostrand, New York, 1949.
21. D. COUCOUVANIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 11, 233.
22. J. CHATT, L. A. DUNCANSON and L. M. VENANZI, *Suomen Kemistilehti, B*, 1956, 23, 75 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, 51, 5559).
23. D. COUCOUVANIS and J. P. FACKLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 2047.
24. G. S. NIKOLOV, N. JORDANOV and K. DAKALAVA, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1970, 6, 723.
25. A. N. BHATT, R. C. FAY, D. F. LEWIS, A. F. LINDMARK and S. H. STRAUSS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 886.
26. K. A. JENSEN and P. H. NILSON, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1966, 20, 597.
27. E. C. ALYEA and B. C. RAMSWAMY, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1970, 6, 441.
28. J. J. ZUCKERMAN, *Adv. Organomet. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 21.
29. V. I. GOLDANSKII, V. V. KHARAPON, O. YUCKHLOBYS-TIN and V. YA ROCHEV in "Chemical Applications of Mössbauer Spectroscopy", eds. V. I. GOLDANSKII and R. H. HERBER, Academic, New York, 1968.
30. B. W. FITSIMMONS, A. A. OWUSU, N. J. SEELEY and A. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 935.
31. C. H. STAFFER and R. H. HERBER, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1973, 56, 175.